

Metallic Uranium in Organic Synthesis. Part II.

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Very recently uranium metal has been introduced in organic synthesis and has been successfully used in Friedel-Crafts', Reformatsky's and Zincke's reactions. It did not give very encouraging results in Ullmann's reaction (Lal and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 389) but highly satisfactory results were obtained in Zincke's reaction where the action of benzyl chloride on hydrocarbons and phenolic ethers was tried. In the present investigation the action of benzyl chloride on toluene, phenol, hydroquinone dimethyl ether, and on higher hydrocarbons such as naphthalene, acenaphthene and diphenyl in presence of uranium metal has been successfully tried and the various products isolated. The study of these reactions is complicated by the fact that in addition to the isomeric monobenzyl derivatives, isomeric dibenzyl derivatives are simultaneously formed during the reaction, isolation and characterisation of which becomes consequently a difficult task.

The action of benzyl chloride on naphthalene was first studied by Frôte in presence of zinc dust (*Compt rend.*, 1873, **76**, 639) and then Mignal (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1877, *ii*, **25**, 27), Vincent and Roux (*ibid.*, 1883, **40**, 163) and Roux (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1887, *vi*, **12**, 289) studied the reaction using zinc dust, fused zinc chloride and anhydrous aluminium chloride respectively as the catalyst. The later authors isolated pure α - and β -benzyl-naphthalenes. Boguski (*Ber.*, 1906, **39**, 2866) using metallic aluminium isolated in addition to the two monobenzyl-naphthalenes, a dibenzyl-naphthalene (m. p. 146.5°).

Dziewonski and Moszew (*Bull. Acad. Polonaise*, 1928, **A**, 283) and Wodelski (*Rocz. Chem.*, 1932, **12**, 266) have isolated several dibenzyl-naphthalenes. The mono- and dibenzyl-naphthalenes have further been studied in great detail in recent years (*Bull. Acad. Polonaise*, 1927, **A**, 273-286 ; 1928, **A**, 283 ; 1930, **A**, 66 ; *Rocz. Chem.*, 1929, **9**, 361).

By the action of benzyl chloride on acenaphthene and diphenyl in presence of uranium, 5-benzyl-acenaphthene and β -(3 or 4) benzyl-acenaphthene and two benzyldiphenyls (m. p. 44-45° and 51.55°) have been isolated respectively.

Attempts were also made to prepare hexanitrodiphenyl from picryl chloride, 4:4'-dinitrodiphenyl from *p*-nitrochlorobenzene but without success. It has also been found that uranium metal cannot be used as neutral reducing agent either in aqueous or aqueous-alcoholic solutions.

Unsuccessful Attempts.

Type of reaction.	Reactants.	Expected products.
1. Ullmann's	Picryl chloride	Hexanitrodiphenyl
2. „	<i>p</i> -Nitrochlorobenzene	4:4'-Dinitrodiphenyl
3. Neutral reduction	Benzophenone	Benzhydrol
4. „	Nitrobenzene	Aniline
5. „	<i>p</i> -Nitrotoluene	<i>p</i> -Toluidine
6. „	Picric acid	Picramic acid
7. Zincke's reaction	Benzyl chloride and benzyl cyanide	Benzyl benzyl- cyanide.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Benzylhydroquinone dimethyl ether.—A mixture of hydroquinone dimethyl ether (16 g.), benzyl chloride (10 g.) and uranium dust (3 g.) was gradually heated in an oil-bath up to 70° when hydrogen chloride was freely evolved. After the first vigorous reaction had subsided the mixture was heated at 110°-120° for 4 hours. The product was extracted with benzene, filtered, washed with water and dried over calcium chloride, and after removal of benzene it was fractionated at ordinary pressure and the fraction at 340°-360° (redistilled at 353°-355°) was identified as benzylquinol dimethyl ether, yield 12.6 g. (66.3%). A deep red viscous residue was left in the distilling flask and on standing for about a month deposited a small amount of a crystalline mass (0.8 g.). It crystallised from boiling alcohol as rhombic tablets, m. p. 104-5° and is under investigation.

o- & p-Benzylphenols.—Benzyl chloride (16 g.), anhydrous phenol (21 g.) and uranium dust (3.5 g.) were heated first at 70° for $\frac{1}{2}$ an hour when a very vigorous reaction took place and then at 120°-130° for 4 hours. The product was filtered hot and then fractionated at ordinary pressure and the fractions boiling at 305°-330° and 360°-370° collected. By repeated fractionation the fraction (b. p. 305-330°) was separated into two fractions (A) distilling at 310-12° and (B) at 320-22°. The fraction (A) crystallised on standing, and the crystals after being pressed between filter papers melted at 20°

and were identified as those of benzylphenol, yield 3 g. (*cf.* Claisen, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1923, 36, 478).

The fraction (B) was a colourless, non-fluorescent thick heavy liquid with fine floral smell, and insoluble in and heavier than water and it dissolves in caustic alkalis but not in ammonia. It crystallised from alcohol in shining plates, m. p. 84°, identified as *p*-benzylphenol (the methyl ether, b. p. 304-5°; the mononitro derivative, m. p. 74-75°), yield 18.7 g. (*cf.* Paterno, *Gazzetta*, 1872, 2, 1; Paterno and Fileti, *ibid.*, 1873, 3, 121, 251; Rennie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1882, 41, 33). (Found C, 84.39; H, 6.61, $C_{13}H_{12}O$ requires C, 84.78; H, 6.52 per cent.)

The fraction at 360-370° (redistilled at 365-67°) which was free from phenolic compounds was identified as *p*-benzylphenol benzyl ether, yield 2.2 g.

Phenyltolylmethane and dibenzyltoluenes from benzyl chloride and toluene.—A mixture of benzyl chloride (25 g.), toluene (46 g.) and uranium dust (4 g.) was gradually heated in an oil-bath up to 90° when a very vigorous reaction took place. After the first vigorous reaction the mixture was heated at 125-135° for 4 hours and filtered hot. The green filtrate having an intense deep violet fluorescence was washed with water, dried and fractionally distilled at ordinary pressure up to 220° and the residue left in the flask fractionated under reduced pressure of 160 mm:

(1) 95-190°; (2) 190-270°; (3) 270-320° temperature rising quickly; (4) 320-330°; (5) 330-380°/30 mm. The fraction (1) was fractionally distilled at ordinary pressure and the fraction above 270° collected and mixed with fraction (2) and fractionally distilled thrice, finally the fraction at 277-279° was identified as pure *p*-benzyltoluene (yield 20 g., 45.5%). (Found: C, 92.04; H, 7.72. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{14}$. C, 92.30; H, 7.69 per cent). It did not solidify even on keeping in a refrigerator for weeks. In chloroform solution it gave with anhydrous $AlCl_3$ a pink colouration (*cf.* Zincke, *Ber.*, 1874, 7, 982).

The fraction (4) was a thick liquid with intense violet fluorescence and having a fine flowery smell. It was redistilled under reduced pressure and the fraction at 280-285°/30 mm. boiling at 392-396° at ordinary pressure was identified as dibenzyltoluene (11 g.). It was a fluorescent oil which did not solidify even on keeping in a refrigerator for weeks. It dissolved in the usual organic solvents and did not form a picrate. (Found: C, 92.3; H, 7.41. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{20}$. C, 92.64; H, 7.35 per cent) (*cf.* Weber and Zincke, *Ber.*, 1874, 7, 1153).

The portion of the first fraction which distilled at 280-300° at ordinary pressure (1 g.) was fractionated and the various fractions did not solidify even when kept in a freezing mixture while dibenzyl, the possibility of formation of which is not remote, boils at 284° and melts at 52°. So evidently dibenzyl does not appear to be formed.

α- & β-Benzylnaphthalenes.—A mixture of benzyl chloride (30 g.), naphthalene (42 g.) and uranium powder (5 g.) was gradually heated in an oil bath up to 65° when a very vigorous reaction took place and then maintained at 120-125° for 3 hours. The pink mixture having an intense blue fluorescence was filtered hot from the metal and then fractionated at ordinary pressure, two fractions A (b.p. 310-365°) and B (b.p. 370-76°) being collected. The fraction (A) was steam distilled in order to free it from traces of naphthalene and then extracted with chloroform and after removal of the latter it was fractionally distilled. A small amount of a colourless oil came over at 300-320° and then the rest of the liquid distilled at 340°-355° and both these oils solidified on keeping in a refrigerator. The fraction boiling at 340-355° after crystallisation from boiling alcohol gave *α*-benzylnaphthalene (16 g.) as rhombic plates, m. p. 57-58°. These were soluble in chloroform, ether, benzene, carbon disulphide and boiling alcohol and on oxidation with concentrated boiling nitric acid gave *α*-naphthylphenylketone, m. p. 73-73·5°; picrate, m. p. 99-100° (*cf. Roux, loc. cit.*). The fraction at 300-320° after several crystallisations from boiling alcohol gave *β*-benzylnaphthalene, m. p. 39-40°. It is soluble in benzene and chloroform even in the cold and identified as *β*-benzylnaphthalene (2 g.).

From the fraction (B) none of the three *α*, *β*- and *γ*-dibenzyl-naphthalenes could be isolated

Phenylacenaphthylmethanes.—A mixture of benzyl chloride (20 g.), acenaphthene (32 g.) and uranium powder (4 g.) was gradually heated in an oil-bath up to 95° when torrents of hydrogen chloride were evolved and after the first vigorous reaction had subsided the temperature of the bath was maintained at 100-110° for 6 hours. The reaction product was extracted with benzene, filtered and after complete removal of benzene fractionally distilled at 15-20 mm., and two fractions collected: (A) b.p. 250-290°, colourless oil, temperature remaining constant at 260-270°; (B) b.p. 300-370°, red oil which did not solidify.

Fraction (A) on redistillation gave a colourless oil (b.p. 260-270°/20 mm.) and on standing it became semi-solid due to the separation of a crystalline mass. After several crystallisations from boiling alcohol the more insoluble portion was obtained as silky white needles, m.p. 106-107° and was identified as 5-benzylacenaphthene (4.2 g.), m.p. 110-11° (cf. Dziewonski and others, *Bull. Soc. chim.* 1904, iii, 31, 373; *Bull. Acad. Polonaise*, 1928, A, 99). The soluble portion was obtained as needles, m.p. 47-49° (picrate, m.p. 100-101°). It was identified as β - (3 or 4)-benzylacenaphthene (3.4 g.). It melts at 45-46° and forms a dipicrate, m.p. 101-102°. The fraction (3) weighed 14 g. and nothing crystalline could be isolated from it.

α - & β -Benzyl-diphenyls.—A mixture of benzyl chloride (14 g.), diphenyl (23 g.) and uranium powder (3 g.) was slowly heated in an oil-bath up to 70° when a very vigorous reaction took place. It was then heated for 4 hours at 120-125°, filtered hot and the filtrate kept in a vacuum desiccator over caustic potash in order to remove the hydrogen chloride present. The product was fractionally distilled at 20 mm. and the fractions collected were: (A) 112-200°, colourless oil, the main fraction coming over at 128-135° and solidifying in the receiver; (B) 200-250°, colourless oil solidifying in the receiver. (C) 340-370°, pale yellow oil which did not solidify even in a freezing mixture (10.8 g.).

Fraction (A) was submitted to redistillation and the fraction below 160° was rejected and the rest redistilled along with (B) when major portion of it distilled at 170-180°. The fraction (a) was a colourless oil quickly solidifying on cooling and a second fraction (b) at 200-230° was a colourless viscous oil (2.3 g.) which did not solidify immediately. The boiling point of pure diphenyl was found to be 130-132°/20 mm. and the rejection of fraction distilling below 150° ensured the absence of diphenyl in the fraction 170-180°. The fraction (a) separated from boiling alcohol in the form of tiny needles, and the first and the least soluble portion on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid was obtained in the form of beautiful long needles, m. p. 44-45° after drying in a vacuum desiccator over caustic potash and was identified as α -benzyl-diphenyl. Even after repeated crystallisations from alcohol and acetic acid its melting point remained unaltered. (Found: C, 93.39; H, 6.65. $C_{19}H_{16}$ requires C, 93.44; H, 6.65 per cent). The alcoholic mother liquor gave another crop of crystals after concentration, m. p. 51-56°, β -benzyl-diphenyl identical with isobenzyl-diphenyl of Goldschmidt (*Monatsh.*, 1881, 2, 432) who by the action of benzyl

chloride on diphenyl in presence of zinc dust isolated *p*-benzylidiphenyl as flat needles from hot glacial acetic and as plates from alcohol, m.p. 85° and *isobenzylidiphenyl* as monosymmetrical needles, m.p. 54°.

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A Short Note on the Chromium Biguanide Complexes.

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Complex compounds of biguanide with bivalent copper, cobalt and nickel have been described long ago (Ratbke, *Ber.*, 1878, **11**, 967; 1879, **12**, 777; Rackmann, *Annalen*, 1911, **376**, 163). The constitution of these compounds is, however, still under dispute. As these compounds are very sparingly soluble in water, the study of their constitution by usual physico-chemical methods is rendered thereby extremely difficult.

We have now, however, succeeded in preparing soluble biguanide complexes of trivalent chromium. The free complex base, which forms the mother substance and from which a series of salts is in the course of preparation, has been obtained as beautiful ruby-red crystals of the following composition: $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_6)_3] \text{H.OH}$, the biguanide molecule acting as a bidentate group and occupying two co-ordinate positions. The compound is, therefore, expected to give rise to optically active enantiomers. The substance is strongly basic and in aqueous solution behaves as a tri-acidic base, as could be concluded from the freezing-point and conductivity data as well as from the titer-value of the base in aqueous solution.

Fuller details about the preparation, properties and constitution of the compound and its derivatives will be published in due course.

Similar compounds with trivalent cobalt atom have also been prepared and will form the subject matter of a separate paper.

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